

Password Security vs. User Compliance: An Ongoing Dilemma

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Abstract

The following paper discusses a series involving password safety and security. Part 1 discusses how passwords have evolved over the past decades. Though the idea of secret codes and discoveries have been around for centuries, in the technical realm this sort of style did not stray far from it. Early on, systems would rely on shared passwords that were much more simpler and in plaintext. Compared to even the Caesar Cipher, we as a civilization have become significantly more advanced over the past few years. Part 2 discusses historical breaches that have happened as a result of companies undermining the CIA, or confidentiality, integrity, availability/authentication for themselves and users. In large business entities like Casinos, less investments into cybersecurity causes them not to lose only money, but loyal customers. Examples such as the aforementioned are set up to remind other large business entities to make the proper investments that will strengthen their livelihood long-term, even if it means the protection costs are difficult to manage. Part 3 discusses my own endeavors in the CodePath course I've taken, regarding multiple assignments and projects, as well as the capstone project that was done at the end of the semester, this portion helps highlight the importance of cybersecurity, and how free programs help accelerate the yearning minds to learn more about internet safety and security. Part 4 involves a case study of roughly 50 students, being asked about how they manage their passwords, from what they prefer to what they actually use. This small yet meaningful dataset acts as a metric to assess the habits of young adults and their interest towards self-security and integrity. Part 5 concludes the paper and acknowledges all of the previous parts' components, as well as reaching a verdict on how well encryption matters to young adults.

Introduction:

“Hello World”. This simple statement is considered a foundation to testing if one’s program runs or works. Even to non-technical individuals, this statement is universally recognized as a pathway to the coding world; it is what allows a computer to speak to us in languages we understand. However, if a series of numbers such as “01001000 01100101 01101100 01101100 01101111 00100000 01010111 01101111 01110010 01101100 01100100” were written instead, the meaning may not be so clear-cut. The series of binary presented is just the phrase “Hello World”. If the phrase “Khoor Zruog” was presented, one would not realize that this technically also means Hello World, but the reason for its ‘uniqueness’ would be due to its encryption known as the Cesar Cipher. The complexity of these phrases all go back to the concept of cryptography, the practice of writing secret codes to turn our aforementioned readable texts into indecipherable texts that only people who follow certain protocols or use certain tools will be able to access or read. This cryptography essentially revolves around the idea of secret messages, which is most prominent in something we use everyday, which are passwords. Though, not all passwords are the same. Some websites may prompt you to include special characters such as the “@” symbol “_” and much more, other sites lack such requirements, and will let you type even the most basic passwords such as (1,2,3,4,5), with little to no checks whatsoever. Naturally, the latter raises a significantly higher security issue. Especially if such passwords are stored in plaintext – implying that there was no other protocol that went into hashing or encrypting the password; making its accessibility to private and confidential information significantly more easy to do so. From the history and growth of secret codes, to the historical breaches that have happened due to an undermining of security, real-world experience, and an assessment examining how many college students truly care about their privacy in the form of -

confidentiality, integrity and authentication for their passwords and keys that keep their personal information private.

Body Paragraph One:

The tech world had only begun to proliferate in the early 1960s, but passwords have been around for hundreds of years. A password, by definition, is referenced as a “subscriber-chosen secret” used as an authentication factor to gain access to private facilities. (*NIST Special Publication 800-63B*, n.d.). In roughly 150 BCE, about ~2000 years ago, Roman soldiers would write on a wooden tablet called a *Tessera* that would be distributed to those on a nightwatch. The tablet would have a secret code or phrase that would be recalled to other Roman soldiers on active duty. This provided the Roman soldiers a huge advantage in patrolling, as the darkness would no longer be an issue when it came to identification anymore. An enemy or infiltrator would easily be recognizable due to the lack of knowledge of the shared code – the shared secret key (Polybius & Macmillan, 2011). Despite being over thousands of years ago this practice follows a modern day symmetric cryptography. Two parties are aware of and “share” their secret key, which in this case takes form in the *Tessera*, and when this phrase is checked alongside another member, they’re verified about whether or not the person patrolling the Roman area is of their own; preventing further access or even engaging in capture if the keys do not match. While the Romans were ahead of their time, they had no way of digitizing such an ancient form of verification. Years later, this became a topic that never quite went away. When MIT computer scientist Emeritus Fernando Corbató invented the compatible time-sharing system in 1961 (*Professor Emeritus Fernando Corbató, MIT Computing Pioneer, Dies at 93*, 2019). The compatible time-sharing system, or CTSS, for short allowed for users to access the same computer, but with passwords stored in plaintext that separated each users’ files to access at their

own leisure. Though arguably primitive, this marked the first computer system to use passwords, and as stated by his colleagues, would 'fundamentally change the way people use information.' (*Professor Emeritus Fernando Corbató, MIT Computing Pioneer, Dies at 93*, 2019). With the passwords being stored in a plaintext file, and with the system allowing individuals to request files to be printed offline via a punched card, it was relatively easy for the hacker, Allan Scherr to conduct the first computer password hack in history (McMillan, 2012). While the simplicity of the password was one of the factors that have led to the hack, it was moreso the lack of *authentication* that had resulted in this hack. For anyone to be able to request a file without proper clearance, the whole system was a poor test of security, even given the current conditions. The Scherr incident, alongside many others, showed once and for all that plaintext storage was a very poor choice when discussing the nature of password security. This would be formally addressed decades later through the SHA family. This approach involved how systems would transform or 'hash' passwords; creating something virtually indecipherable to the human eye. Though there were many iterations of the 'SHA', the ones that stand out are SHA-1 and SHA-2, as their appearances fundamentally changed the world of encryption today. SHA-1 developed by the NSA experienced a quick adoption in the early 2000s, due to its nature to hash plaintext passwords that would be considered "useless" for incoming attackers. This effect of hashing would also change password integrity entirely as changing even the slightest thing in the password: e.g. a comma, or pressing spacebar would result in a 'completely unique hash (Lim 2017). This effect, known as the avalanche effect, would go on to lay the foundation for future hashing algorithms. However, despite it's success in both password safety and data integrity, it was not entirely secure. By 2010, many organizations have stopped the use of SHA-1 due to discovering its vulnerabilities. Researchers at Google and CWI were able to crack SHA's

algorithm after 9-quintillion SHA-1 calculations (a lot of computing power). In the end, these same researchers were able to provide two unique PDF files that produced the same exact SHA-1 hash value. The moment this was discovered, industries began to slowly shift away from using SHA-1, because despite the computing power it took to crack it, and the attack being controlled, even the possibility of it threatens the CIA of an institution or company. A hacker or crime syndicate at any moment could in a malicious file in place of a trusted one, and the system would still flag it as safe. This type of pre-determined safety is a necessity in the cyber world, because you can never pinpoint just how many resources a determined individual has to break into a system or pipeline of systems (Lim 2017). Fortunately, the remnants of vulnerability were left behind and later developed into SHA-2. The family of cryptographic hash functions that include SHA-256, SHA-384 AND SHA-512 offer a significantly stronger collision resistance than their predecessor (Cobb, 2022). For reference, SHA-1 had a 160 bit hash length which became questionable due to the relative ease of vulnerabilities that could be matched when hashing. These longer bit lengths that we see from SHA-2 produces an exponential improvement. With the number of collisions going from 2^{80} all the way up to 2^{128} , requiring significantly more computing power to even attempt collision attacks (Cobb 2022). SHA-256 especially has one of the most widely used hashing algorithms in the world, most notably being used in the Bitcoin network - the most expensive digital currency, where it verifies transactions and generates digital signatures that confirm data integrity without ever exposing the original content (Ledger Academy, 2023). Talk about argon, then include a salting image of sorts. However, the key characteristic that makes SHA-256 ideal for Bitcoin: its speed, is actually its greatest weakness when it comes to password storage. A function that processes billions of hashes at a time can be used to the same leverage by an attacker, randomly guessing millions of combinations with

enough computing power and brute force would lead to its eventual downfall. As previously discussed, 'breaking' a cryptographic hash function makes it lose technical value in the security world. Fortunately this concern gave rise to additions that caused a deliberate slowness that essentially creates adaptive password hashing functions. These algorithms, like Bcrypt, Scrypt and Argon2 are intentionally built to be resource intensive through a process called salting, where a unique value is added to a password before hashing, ensuring that even in the event of two identical passwords, the product would produce entirely different outputs; an effective combatant against large scale attacks by making such attempts more costly (OWASP, n.d.).

Image of a salting process using the ARGON2 hash. - Courtesy of Professor Bill Buchanan¹

The history of passwords and security has developed significantly since its origins. With every new attempt at protection, there is an equal attempt at infiltration. As the following breaches will show, failure to keep one's CIA triad in check risks far more than security alone.

Body Paragraph Two:

Despite the cryptographic advancements made over the decades, organizations entrusted with protecting user data have repeatedly failed to implement them. For instance, in 2012, 117 million LinkedIn emails and passwords were hacked and posted publicly online. LinkedIn stored

¹ <https://medium.com/asecuritysite-when-bob-met-alice/argon2-bcrypt-scrypt-or-pbkdf2-e449c34cce72>

passwords through unsalted SHA-1 hashes, 90 percent of the 117 million exposed passwords were cracked within 72 hours of the data being posted for sale. The absence of adding a salt meant that there were likely cases of unique passwords, something that a salt like ARGON2, bcrypt could have prevented. Due to the nature of LinkedIn's poor recognition security, the attack was practically seamless using pre-made 'rainbow tables', an already matched list of scrambled and unscrambled passwords. The reason rainbow tables are so effective in this case ultimately comes down to this sole idea of a salt being absent, or the lack of. This led to the vulnerability of identical or near identical passwords, which consequently, produce near identical hashes almost every single time. All the hackers would need to do is simply precompute a massive lookup table of hash(password) = plaintext pairs offline, which would then allow them to reference that against the stolen database relatively quickly. LinkedIn was at an even greater disadvantage due to the utilization of SHA-1, as its speed would lead to a faster run, leading to a table being built faster and searched. What made this attack especially concerning was that it was initially thought only 6.5 million accounts to be affected, but the data breaching has been so unknown for so long that it wasn't revealed until it had reached such an extremely large number like 117 million four years later (Finkle, 2016). On the contrary, that same track could be utilized in LinkedIn's favor, using the rainbow tables as an outline or premise to create stronger restrictions in password creation, ensuring that each individual's password is significantly different and unique, resulting in unique hashes that rainbow tables may have difficulty picking up on (McMahon & Zhang, 2018). Similarly in 2013, Yahoo was exploited through their passwords being hashed with MD5, an algorithm that was already known to be weak by this time. MD5 produces a 128-bit output, putting its theoretical birthday bound at 2^{64} , a threshold that was already within the reach of experienced hackers at the time of the attack. MD5 has been producing collisions since 2004, a

full nine years before the aforementioned breach. A company as large as Yahoo using MD5 for password storage almost a decade later after its demonstration of collision vulnerabilities is not just a technical mishap. This attack represents a prime example of a system not upholding their CIA (confidentiality, integrity, and Authenticity) and suffering the clear consequences that could have otherwise been avoided. Hackers were able to quickly look up MD5 hashes in precomputed databases and were able to recover original passwords, as well as encrypted security questions that were stored. A possible prevention to this attack would have been a migration to SHA-2 or an adaptive hashing algorithm like ARGON2 years before the breach. Further encryption storage of the security questions and having periodic security checks over the site would have potentially caught the outdated use of the MD5 hash too. It is attacks like these that show why a migration is absolutely necessary when a previous cryptographic hash is cracked (Hautala, 2016).

Furthermore, in that same year, Adobe was hacked to a similar issue. In Adobe's password help/creation center, a human vulnerability was exposed showing that individuals would often just put their actual password as part of the "password hints". As a result, this made the job of hackers relatively easy, since most accounts relied on ease of use rather than the nature and security of their account itself; essentially giving out their passwords directly to the attackers (Huntress 2025). What made Adobe's breach technically worse than it appeared on the surface of things was the type of encryption mode they chose. Adobe used 3DES in ECB (electronic codebook) mode which essentially encrypts identical blocks of data identically. This means patterns in the original password survive into the ciphertext. Researchers were able to cross-reference these ciphertext patterns against the plaintext hints that the non technical users had provided, allowing these hackers to quickly reverse engineer these passwords at a large scale. Unlike the avalanche effect that was previously brought up, Adobe essentially performed

the opposite, as similar inputs stayed similar visibly even after encryption, practically handing away private information to these attackers. A possible fix for this would be 2FA like Authy which provides a time-based-one-time password that mathematically generates new codes every 30 seconds, ensuring no new code is the exact same. So in the case of a password or credentials being stolen, hackers would not be able to do much of anything due to the code quickly becoming useless; 2FA would act as an extra (yet necessary) security measure.

Image of an Authy demonstration of 2FA. Courtesy of [Authy's official feature page](#).²

However, these protective measures only work when the developers building these systems understand the code and documentation used to develop and integrate these security measures into their pre-existing applications. With the extreme rise of 'vibe-coding' with the help of multiple LLM's like ChatGPT, Claude, Gemini, and more, individuals with non-technical backgrounds are now able to generate entire web applications, mobile apps, and much more. The

²<https://www.authy.com/features/>

application may look good and run as intended, but it opens an entirely new scope of security issues. The lack of CIA mindfulness is exactly what led to the downfall of a recently vibecoded social-network app: "Moltbook". The hack resulted from a simple technical issue, where researchers at Wiz inspected the publicly available JavaScript code and found that the API key was publicly exposed in the code. This single key would allow users to unlock the entire production database, without ever needing the lead to login. This led to 35,000 user email addresses being exposed and thousands of private messages being leaked to the public, all within the span of three days (Wiz, 2026). What non-technical individuals seem to not understand is that using ai tools to build applications for you may result in unnecessary or unchecked code if not prompted or specified properly. In other words, you have to be as specific as possible, or the AI will make awkward assumptions to "fill in the gaps" between necessary and functionality. Moving forward, the team should try invoking a series of test cases and checks to ensure that nothing could happen to the integrity of their app before deployment. The most difficult thing these organizations had lost was not the wealth or investment, but the trust and loyalty of users that trusted for the secure and safety of the privacy of their credentials. This is something that cannot be bought, and is truly worth something grand. This is not to discourage the use of AI in building as it does promote productivity, but trusting it entirely is bound to pose some risks, especially in larger scale platforms. This is precisely why cybersecurity education matters. It is not meant to discourage innovation, but to ensure that those building these systems understand what they are responsible for securing. Programs like CodePath have made that education more accessible than ever, offering free, structured exposure to the very concepts that breaches like Moltbook's make extremely relevant.

Body Paragraph Three:

CodePath is a non-profit organization that provides thousands of students each semester with free technical courses covering the fundamentals of various tech fields. One such course is CYB 101, a 10-week program covering social engineering, malware attacks, networking, and access control. The program is designed to give students foundational knowledge of cybersecurity concepts through hands-on simulations that replicate real-world cyber threats (CodePath, 2021). As a former student at the organization, I would have to say the most prominent aspect of the course that stood out was less of the technical aspect of things, but rather the social engineering portions. Learning how security failures always in some way trace back to human behavior, more specifically, human error. In the capture the flag exercises, there were modules that asked to decrypt encrypted text using the application "CyberChef". This local web app is home to numerous hashing algorithms, from SHA0 to SHA-2 which consists of the most modern and secure hashes like SHA-256 and SHA-512. A recurring challenge in these exercises involved messages that had been encoded or encrypted multiple times over. The correct solution required students to recognize that a single decryption pass was not always the 'right answer'. Though if the students reached that point they could come up to that conclusion, since the answer was somewhat legible. This led to a common mistake of partial decryption, as the actual answer was double encoded. For instance, there was a string that read: "TGJoIG5lciB0cmdndmF0IGpuZXpyZSwgeWJieCBxcnJjcmU=" the hint provided only showed that the Base64 decode was "Lbh ner trggvat jnezre, ybbx qrrcre", where lots of students tended to stop. Their justification was that despite the message looking gibberish, it was also in English plaintext, so they were under the assumption that it would be recognized in the pattern. The last step that very few students got was decoding that string with ROT13, getting you the final and

complete answer of: "You are getting warmer, look deeper". It's this kind of diligence that reflects the world of cybersecurity and user compliance, and how individuals will often do the bare minimum, or "what works" to move onto the next task immediately (GCHQ, 2026). This type of complacency, or lack of technical diligence is exactly what leads to errors misconstrued in the modern day. This kind of behavioral pattern is not unique to controlled exercises. To better understand how these habits manifest in the real world, a survey was conducted among roughly 50 college students to assess how they manage their passwords, what they prioritize, and whether their practices reflect any meaningful awareness of the security concepts that have been discussed throughout this paper.

Body Paragraph Four:

A survey was conducted from January to May 2026 among approximately 50 college students at the College of Staten Island, assessing their understanding of personal password safety, their preferred management habits, and the gap between what they know and what they actually practice. When students were prompted to rate their overall knowledge of cybersecurity, the majority of the respondents (43.1%) placed themselves on a moderate level, while only 19.6% rated themselves at a higher level and 35.3% of people rated themselves at a 'low' or 'very low' level. This self-reflection allows us to see a small portion of how the population sees themselves in regard to security compliance and sets itself up for the remainder of the form.

How would you rate your overall knowledge of cybersecurity?

51 responses

Pie chart showcasing the majority population deeming they have ‘moderate’ knowledge of cybersecurity. - Courtesy of Abdel Mahmoud’s research³

This is most reflected in the survey section that regards familiarity of attacks, with Dos attacks - the least relevant to password security seems to be the most frequented knowledge piece. Attacks like Zero-day and ransomware which more so target one's individual credentials are ranked the lowest out of the options. An average of 42% as compared to the 70% Dos attacks have.

Which of the following threats are you familiar with? (Select all that apply)

51 responses

³https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1-hLiawyMs_w2PJ3WIpEwtyhO4U-goFNuiE-QVcyHfrI/edit

Bar chart showcasing the majority population is most knowledgeable of a DoS attack. - Courtesy of Abdel Mahmoud's research⁴

The strongest compliance gap reveals itself when we examine the actual password behavior. 76.5% of students admitted to *reusing the same password* across multiple accounts. This practice is exactly what contributed to the aforementioned LinkedIn and Yahoo attacks.

Pie chart showcasing how the majority of individuals tend to reuse their passwords in comparison to updating or creating a new one entirely. - Courtesy of Abdel Mahmoud's research⁵

This discovery in tandem with the fact that the majority of users 43.1% only "change their passwords when prompted to" shows the need for more security, safety and care among the generations. While there were some notable findings like how 82.4% of individuals use 2FA authentication for their password and browsing safety, the previous discoveries demonstrate an implication that these individuals were *required* or heavily influenced for such an implementation to be used.

⁴https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1-hLiawyMs_w2PJ3WIpEwtyhO4U-goFNuiE-QVcyHfrI/edit

⁵https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1-hLiawyMs_w2PJ3WIpEwtyhO4U-goFNuiE-QVcyHfrI/edit

Do you currently use 2FA for your passwords?

51 responses

Pie chart showcasing how the majority of individuals use 2FA (two factor authentication) when configuring passwords. - Courtesy of Abdel Mahmoud's research⁶

An example of this could be CUNYFirst's new outlook authentication, which requires a 2FA to be set up in order to access one's email's Brightspace, and of course assignments. Overall, this shows us that the majority of individuals are not against the extra steps to secure their credentials, but will not go through themselves unless they are unable to navigate the application otherwise. Overall, the data suggests that compliance is not a matter of resistance but of requirement. When security is built into the system, compliance follows. When it is left to the individual, e.g. voluntarily, it does not. Young adults are not opposed to protecting themselves, but few will do so unless the alternative is being locked out entirely. This raises a broader question that extends well beyond cybersecurity: should users be given the freedom to manage their own security, knowing that without enforced requirements, most will not? The data

⁶https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1-hLiawyMs_w2PJ3WIpEwtyhO4U-goFNuiE-QVcyHfrI/edit

suggests that voluntary compliance is largely ineffective among young adults, and that meaningful protection tends to only follow when it is structurally mandated. This is not unique to the digital world. Human behavior across most domains tends toward the path of least resistance unless an external incentive or consequence demands otherwise.

Concluding Statements:

To summarize, the evolution of password security has come a long way. From Roman soldiers exchanging secret phrases on a Tessera, to plaintext files on shared terminals, to modern adaptive hashing algorithms and salting techniques, the history of authentication has always been a race between those who protect and those who exploit. Companies can lose time, investments, and money, but losing the trust of their users is the one thing that cannot simply be patched or reimbursed. The breaches of Yahoo, LinkedIn, and Adobe proved that much. Our research further revealed that young adults are not entirely opposed to securing their accounts, but rarely do so on their own initiative unless a system demands it of them. Granted, the dataset is small in the grand scheme of things, but despite that limitation, the results seem persistent: this is the ongoing dilemma that password security presents. The tools exist, the knowledge is growing, and the willingness is there when the situation calls for it. What remains is the challenge of designing systems and cultivating habits that do not wait for a breach to make security feel necessary. As technology continues to advance, at an exponential rate thanks to AI, these factors will no longer collide, but rather merge, for both a securitable and equitable consumer experience.

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